

PREBUCKLING AND COLLAPSE RESPONSE OF THIN-WALLED COMPOSITE CYLINDERS SUBJECTED TO BENDING LOADS

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ABSTRACT

A numerical and experimental study of the behavior of unstiffened thin-walled graphite-epoxy cylindrical shells subjected to bending loads is presented. Eight-ply quasi-isotropic and orthotropic shells were subjected to bending in a special test fixture. The experimental prebuckling, buckling, and postbuckling responses are compared to predictions from geometrically nonlinear analyses. It is found that a geometrically nonlinear boundary layer behavior characterizes the prebuckling responses. Discrepancies between predicted and observed strain amplitudes indicate that shape imperfections and other localized imperfections influence the prebuckling responses, causing a reduction in the predicted buckling resistance. Ultimate failure is attributed to excessive postbuckling deformations.

Keywords: bending, boundary layer, buckling, composite cylindrical shell, geometric shape imperfection, nonlinear analysis, postbuckling, prebuckling

1. INTRODUCTION

The response and failure characteristics of composite shell structures subjected to typical fuselage loads must be well understood before advanced composite materials can be used effectively for transport aircraft fuselage structures. In this study, bending loads are applied to thin-walled composite circular cylinders in order to simulate one of the primary flight loads experienced by typical transport fuselage structures. The cylinders studied here are considered relatively short so that collapse is characterized by short-wavelength buckling along the length of the compression side of the shell. This collapse response is similar to the axisymmetric collapse of a cylinder subjected to axial compression. The critical axial force resultant associated with the axisymmetric compression buckling of an imperfection-free anisotropic cylinder can be computed from the work of Tennyson et al. [1]. For the practical case of balanced symmetric laminates, the critical bending moment can be computed from the relation

$$M_{cr} = 2\pi R \sqrt{E_{\theta} H D_{11}}, \quad (1)$$

where D_{11} is the axial laminate bending stiffness, H is the shell wall thickness, E_{θ} is the smeared laminate circumferential inplane stiffness, and R is the midsurface radius. The number of axial half-waves, m , of the associated axisymmetric mode shape is computed from the relation

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$$\frac{m\pi}{L} = \frac{\pi}{\lambda} = \left[\frac{D_{11}R^2}{E_\theta H} \right]^{1/4}, \quad (2)$$

where L is the shell length, and λ is the half-wavelength of the mode shape. The parameter λ is also a characteristic half-wavelength associated with the prebuckling responses. The corresponding end-rotation, Ω_{cr} , and maximum compressive strain, ϵ_x^{cr} , are computed from the beam bending equation

$$\Omega_{cr} = \frac{M_{cr}L}{2E_x I} = \frac{L}{2R} \cdot \epsilon_x^{cr}, \quad (3)$$

where I is the shell cross-section moment of inertia and E_x is the smeared laminate axial inplane stiffness.

Although Equations (1), (2), and (3) are based on a simplified membrane prebuckling assumption, it can be expected that they will give a first approximation of the buckling conditions, so long as boundary effects can be neglected. However, as the cylinders become shorter, boundary conditions cannot be neglected and more rigorous study of the prebuckling responses is generally required to obtain an accurate solution.

The present work considers both a numerical and experimental investigation of composite cylinders in bending. Five eight-ply graphite-epoxy shells with a length-to-radius ratio of 2 and a radius-to-thickness ratio of approximately 160 were tested. Three different layups were investigated. These were a quasi-isotropic $[\mp 45/0/90]_S$ layup, an axially-stiff $[\mp 45/0_2]_S$ layup, and a hoop-stiff $[\mp 45/90_2]_S$ layup.

The analyses will be discussed in the following section, followed by a description of the bending fixture, specimens, and testing procedure. The test results will then be presented and compared to the analyses.

2. ANALYSIS

The specimen geometry and loading is described in Figure 1 (a). Bending is induced by imposing known end-rotations, Ω , on the cylinder ends. The ends are assumed to be clamped and remain circular during loading. The corresponding bending moments, M , are computed from the analyses. Both a geometrically nonlinear special purpose analysis [2] and the STAGS finite element program [3] were employed to predict the prebuckling responses of the imperfection-free shells. Measured shape imperfections were incorporated in the finite element analysis to gauge their effect on the prebuckling and collapse responses.

The geometrically nonlinear special purpose analysis is based on Donnell's nonlinear kinematics and equilibrium equations. The solution is obtained by writing the equilibrium equations as a set of eight coupled first-order nonlinear partial differential equations. The response variables are expanded as a truncated Fourier series in the circumferential direction, and are substituted into the first-order form of the equilibrium equations. The resulting set of coupled nonlinear ordinary differential equations are solved numerically for the axial dependency of the response variables with a finite difference scheme in conjunction with Newton's method to obtain full-field solutions for the midsurface displacements, force and moment resultants, and inplane strains and stresses. The solutions obtained from this method were found to be in excellent agreement with the solutions obtained from the STAGS finite element program. In addition, it was found that the solutions obtained from the special purpose program were computed at a significantly reduced computational cost so that it was found to be an efficient research tool. The prebuckling solutions were also computed for the case of the measured shape imperfections with the STAGS program. The measured surface shape of each shell was included in the finite element analysis in the form of an initial strain imperfection.

The buckling responses were computed with the STAGS program assuming both perfect and imperfect geometries. The buckling end-rotations and corresponding bending moments were computed from a linear bifurcation buckling analysis which was conducted relative to a nonlinear pre-

buckling state. Both the prebuckling and buckling boundary conditions were assumed to be fully clamped.

The postbuckling responses were computed with the finite element program including the measured shape imperfections. An arc-length path continuation algorithm was required to compute solutions beyond buckling due to the highly unstable nature of the initial postbuckling behavior. This procedure involved considerable computational expense due to the small step-size increments required to overcome local critical points. Also, solution difficulties were often encountered due to the presence of secondary solution paths.

3. EXPERIMENT

A special bending fixture and test specimens were designed and fabricated for the present investigation. Each specimen was layed-up by hand from AS4/3502* graphite-epoxy prepreg tape. The specimen wall constructions, average wall thickness, radius-to-thickness ratios, and classical buckling parameters are summarized in Table 1. The length-to-radius ratio was 2 and the nominal midsurface

Table 1. Test specimen summary

Specimen	Layup	H , mm	$\frac{R}{H}$	M_{cr} , N-m	Ω_{cr} , degrees	ϵ_x^{cr} , $\mu\epsilon$	$\frac{\lambda}{L}$	m
CYL-1A	$[\mp 45 / 0 / 90]_S$	0.950	160	15 630	0.207	3 610	0.067	15.0
CYL-1B	$[\mp 45 / 0 / 90]_S$	0.953	160	15 680	0.207	3 617	0.067	15.0
CYL-3A	$[\mp 45 / 0_2]_S$	0.968	156	10 731	0.098	1 697	0.083	12.0
CYL-4A	$[\mp 45 / 90_2]_S$	0.937	163	16 170	0.484	8 383	0.056	17.9
CYL-4B	$[\mp 45 / 90_2]_S$	0.909	167	15 714	0.465	8 114	0.055	18.2

radius was approximately 15.2 cm for all specimens. The buckling values in this table represent the classical applied bending moment, end-rotation, and maximum compressive strain defined in Equations (1) and (3). The last two columns in this table are the half-wavelength parameters defined in Equation (2). The material properties for AS4/3502 given by [4] were adjusted according to a rule of mixtures procedure to account for a higher-than-nominal fiber volume fraction attributed to the specimen fabrication process. The resulting average mechanical properties are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Mechanical properties^a

E_1 , GPa	E_2 , GPa	G_{12} , GPa	ν_{12}
161.1	12.1	7.10	0.285

a. The average ply thickness is 0.118 mm.

The schematic of the test fixture and specimen loading rings is shown in Figures 1 (b) and (c), respectively. Bending loads were applied symmetrically to the shell by rotating the fixture moment arms about the pivot pins shown in Figure 1 (b). Rotation of the moment arms was controlled by the vertical motion of two hydraulic jacks. Hydraulic pressure was split uniformly between the jacks by means of a flow divider. The specimens were clamped to the test fixture via of a set of internal and external aluminum loading rings, shown in Figure 1 (c). The specimen ends were inserted into annular grooves between the internal and external loading rings. The annular grooves were filled with a low-temperature melting-point alloy which served to lock the specimen into place. Circumferential grooves in the loading rings and stepped fiberglass tabs on the ends of the specimens provided a means to react tensile loads. The surface of each shell was accurately measured after the loading rings

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Figure 1. Shell geometry, loading, test fixture, and loading rings.

were mounted. The shape imperfections were then obtained from a map of the shell surface in the form of a Fourier series which was incorporated into the STAGS analysis.

Surface strains were measured at over 60 locations on each specimen with pairs of back-to-back strain gages. Applied forces were measured with calibrated load cells and displacements were measured with direct current differential transformers. The operation of the bending fixture was monitored by measuring strains and displacements at appropriate locations directly on the fixture.

The specimens were loaded to failure quasi-statically and strain, displacement, and applied force data were recorded electronically at the rate of 1 reading per second during the tests. All tests were video recorded and still photos were taken before and after loading. Each cylinder was loaded until buckling occurred. Cylinders that did not show significant visible material damage after buckling were re-buckled and then loaded until failure.

4. RESULTS

As a view of the overall behavior, the measured moment versus end-rotation responses are illustrated for three representative specimens in Figure 2 (a). The bending moments and end-rotations in this figure have been normalized by the classical buckling moment and end-rotation of the quasi-isotropic specimen CYL-1A (see Table 1). These moment and rotation normalization factors are denoted as M_{cr}^{quasi} and Ω_{cr}^{quasi} , respectively. The prebuckling, buckling, and postbuckling responses are indicated in the figure. It can be seen that the prebuckling moment-rotation response is linear for each cylinder. The prebuckling slopes of each specimen, and hence, the bending stiffnesses, vary according to the individual laminate inplane stiffnesses, E_x . The buckling events were indicated by a distinct 'popping' sound and the simultaneous appearance of large diamond-shaped buckles on the compression side. The moment-rotation response corresponding to the buckling events exhibits a dramatic reduction in bending moment and an increase in end-rotation. The initial postbuckling loading paths reflect a significant reduction in bending stiffness due to the effect of the large diamond-shaped buckles on the shell cross-section moment of inertia. Further loading in the postbuckling range was accompanied by pronounced definition of the buckles and subsequent visible and audible material damage. Changes in the postbuckling deflection shapes, referred to here as secondary postbuckling shapes, were accompanied by an additional 'popping' sound. Secondary postbuckling shapes were observed before the failure of the $[\mp 45/0/90]_5$ and the $[\mp 45/0]_5$ specimens. Material failure typically occurred in the regions of severe bending gradients associated with the nodal lines of the deformed shapes.

Measured prebuckling axial surface strain profiles are compared to the predicted strains for three representative specimens in Figures 2 (b), (c), and (d) at the outer surface of the shell wall. The

strains corresponding to the perfect specimens were computed from the special purpose analysis and the strains corresponding to the imperfect specimens were computed from the STAGS analysis. Comparisons are made at the two values of end-rotation indicated in each of the figures and all strain values are normalized with respect to the appropriate classical axial buckling strain (see Table 1). These two end-rotation values correspond to 45% and 90% of the measured buckling values. The geometrically nonlinear behavior is evident near the ends of each shell when comparing the experimental, perfect, and imperfect strain responses at the two rotation values. It is seen that the characteristics of the boundary layer are a function of the loading level as well as the layup. The characteristic half-wavelength parameters, λ , given in Table 1 are indicated in the strain profiles of Figure 2. It can be seen in these figures that the predicted and measured values of λ/L are in excellent agreement.

In comparing the predicted imperfect strain responses to the predicted perfect responses, it is seen that the shape imperfections have the effect of perturbing the axial strains outside of the boundary

Figure 2. Moment-rotation and prebuckling axial surface strain comparison.

layer regions. Comparing the measured responses to the predicted responses shows very good correlation at the lower of the two loading levels, but only fair correlation in the boundary layer region at the higher loading level. The largest discrepancies are apparent in the responses of the $[\mp 45/0_2]_S$ shell. The strain amplitudes are under-predicted in this specimen at $\Omega/\Omega=0.82$ and it appears that the length of the boundary layer is longer than predicted for this loading level. This discrepancy indicates that the axial strain experienced by the shell is more compressive than assumed in the analyses, suggesting that the boundary layer responses are sensitive to localized imperfections, other than the measured shape imperfections. It is clear from Figure 2 that the analyses correctly predict the character of the boundary layer region.

The finite element buckling predictions for both the geometrically perfect and imperfect shells are compared to the experimental buckling values in Table 3. The finite element results are given as the percent difference between the predicted and measured values. The bending moment and end-rotation values in this table represent the average of the values measured at both ends of the shells and are normalized with respect to the corresponding classical buckling values given in Table 1. The number of times each shell was buckled is indicated in Table 3. Only the initial buckling values are reported in this table. The postbuckled shapes were unchanged in the case of repeat-tests.

Table 3. Comparison of buckling values^a

Specimen		Experiment			STAGS perfect shell		STAGS imperfect shell	
Specimen No.	Layup	$\frac{M_{EXP}}{M_{cr}}$	$\frac{\Omega_{EXP}}{\Omega_{cr}}$	No. of loadings	M_{FE}^* %	Ω_{FE}^* %	M_{FE}^* %	Ω_{FE}^* %
CYL-1A	$[\mp 45/0/90]_S$	0.793	0.831	2 ^b	29.5	23.2	20.3	14.6
CYL-1B	$[\mp 45/0/90]_S$	0.852	0.877	3	19.8	16.5	7.9	4.9
CYL-3A	$[\mp 45/0_2]_S$	0.933	0.916	2 ^b	16.2	17.9	14.9	16.3
CYL-4A	$[\mp 45/90_2]_S$	0.686	0.721	1	35.4	26.1	28.9	20.0
CYL-4B	$[\mp 45/90_2]_S$	0.734	0.775	1	28.7	19.4	6.9	1.0

a. $M_{FE}^* = (M_{FE} - M_{EXP})/M_{EXP} \times 100\%$ and $\Omega_{FE}^* = (\Omega_{FE} - \Omega_{EXP})/\Omega_{EXP} \times 100\%$. Finite element predictions and experimental observations are indicated by the subscripts 'FE' and 'EXP', respectively.

b. A reduction in buckling resistance was observed in the final loading.

It is seen from Table 3 that the classical and the finite element predictions over-estimate the measured buckling values in every case. Buckling analyses of the perfect shells over-estimate the measured values by 16% to 35%. The incorporation of the measured shape imperfections in the finite element analyses results in a reduction of the buckling moments and rotations with respect to the perfect shells by 1% to 22% so that the measured buckling values are over-estimated by 1% to 29%. Comparing the predicted buckling moments and end-rotations for the $[\mp 45/0/90]_S$ specimens as well as the $[\mp 45/90_2]_S$ specimens indicates that the measured shell-specific shape imperfections can result in significantly different buckling values.

The buckling shapes corresponding to the finite element predictions of Table 3 are shown in Figure 3 for three representative specimens. For purposes of example, buckling shapes are presented for both the perfect and imperfect specimens in this figure. It is seen that buckling is confined to the compression side in each case and that the buckled shapes appear to be skewed. This skewing phenomenon can be attributed to the presence of the anisotropic bending stiffnesses, D_{16} and D_{26} , and has been observed to occur in the buckling of axially compressed anisotropic shells [5].

The postbuckling deformation shapes observed in the experiment and predicted by the nonlinear analysis indicate large deflections on the compression side of the shell. The postbuckling shapes were dissimilar to the buckling shapes observed in Figure 3. The experimentally observed postbuckling

Figure 3. Predicted mode shapes for perfect and imperfect shells.

shapes were outlined and traced for all specimens with the exception of CYL-1A. Radially inward buckles, secondary buckles, and visible material damage were noted on the traces. The trace for the CYL-3A shell is shown in Figure 4 (a). Both symmetric and asymmetric shapes with either two or three axial half-waves were observed to occur. Material damage appeared to be initiated near nodal lines of the deformed shapes. Zones of material damage were visible at discrete locations for both the quasi-isotropic and axially-stiff cylinders, while extensive circumferential damage zones were visible for the hoop-stiff cylinders.

The postbuckling moment-rotation response curve computed with the STAGS analysis is shown for the $[\pm 45/0/2]_S$ shell in Figure 4 (b). The prebuckling equilibrium path, designated by points ① and ②, is linear while the postbuckling path, designated by points ③ through ⑦, exhibits scalloped-shaped branches. Stable equilibrium solutions are indicated by the solid lines and unstable solutions are indicated by the broken lines in this figure. Each branch of the postbuckling path represents a complex equilibrium configuration with the bending stiffness defined by the slope of the moment-rotation relation. The prebuckling deformation patterns near the bifurcation point, labeled as point ③, and at the final converged solution, point ⑦, are also shown in this figure. The prebuckling deformations are scaled by a factor of 100 and the postbuckling deformations are scaled by a factor of 3 in these figures. The final postbuckled shape at point ⑦ in Figure 4 (b) shows striking similarities to the trace of the experimentally observed postbuckling shape shown in Figure 4 (a).

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Both the measured and predicted prebuckling strains exhibited a geometrically nonlinear behavior in the bending boundary layer region near the ends of the cylinders. It was shown that the characteristic half-wavelength of the boundary layer is related to stiffness and geometrical parameters of the shells. Discrepancies between the measured and predicted strain amplitudes in the boundary layer region suggest that the boundary layer responses are sensitive to localized imperfections in addition to the measured shape imperfections. A rapid growth in the amplitude and axial length of the boundary layer responses indicate the onset of buckling.

Classical predictions significantly overestimate the buckling end-rotations and moments. Consideration of measured shape imperfections significantly improves the buckling predictions in some cases. Discrepancies between measured and predicted buckling end-rotations and moments indicate a need for a more detailed understanding of the effect of localized imperfections on the prebuckling responses. Deflection patterns predicted by the bifurcation buckling analyses were not observed in the experiments due to the unstable nature of the postbuckling path.

(a) Observed postbuckling pattern.

(b) Predicted postbuckling response.

Figure 4. Observed postbuckling pattern and postbuckling analysis for $[\mp 45/0_2]_5$ shell CYL-3A.

A collapse analysis demonstrated a scalloped-shaped postbuckling equilibrium path. Each stable branch of the scalloped-shaped postbuckling path was found to represent a complex deflection pattern. The computed deflection patterns showed striking similarities to those observed in the experiments. Material failure was observed to occur along nodal lines of the postbuckling deflection patterns.

Acknowledgments

The work reported on herein is being supported by the Aircraft Structures Branch of the NASA Langley Research Center through the NASA-Virginia Tech Composites Program, Grant NAG-1-343. The Grant Monitor is Dr. J. H. Starnes, Jr. The financial support of the grant is greatly appreciated.

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